

MILITARY CAMPAIGNS OF AMIR TEMUR

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Introduction: Amir Temur's activity in ancient times and the Middle Ages is considered one of the three great generals. These are: Alexander Makedonskiy, Chigizkhan and Amir Temur. They worked in different eras and under completely different historical conditions. Therefore, it is difficult to compare them. Nevertheless, French and Russian researchers studied the lives of these great generals and gave the highest praise to Amir Temur. In 1361, Temur got closer to Amir Husayn and the two governors were united and had the opportunity to resist the Mughal khans. The event that happened in Timur's life and left a scar on him for life took place in Seistan in 1362. During the battle, Amir Temur was seriously injured by a bow arrow from his right slave's elbow and right leg. After the death of Tughluq Temur, in 1363, the Mongol khan Ilyashoja, who was expelled from the land of Movarounnahr, again started to move towards Movarounnahr with a large army in order to take possession of his former possessions. It was also known that the Mughal Khan was particularly angry with his opponents. In 1363-1364, Temur and Husayn defeated the Mongols three times. Timur and Husayn gathered as many military forces as possible for the upcoming fierce conflict. This battle, which went down in history under the name "Mud Battle", took place between Chinoz and Tashkent on May 22, 1365. Amir Temur Husayn was defeated in the battle due to his weakness and incompetence and returned to Samarkand. In this situation, the warlords take the defense of Samarkand to their slaves. The main goal of the participants of the movement was the fight against the Mongol invaders and oppressive local groups. Besides Mavlonzade, Khordak Bukhari and Abu Bakr Kalavi also joined the defense leadership. The Mongols, who did not know that the city was defended, believed that they would capture it in one attempt. At the beginning of the attack, the chieftains of the Mongol army, led by Mavlonzada, inflicted heavy losses on the enemy with the help of bows. During the preparations for the next siege, an infectious disease began to spread among the troops of Ilyashoja. As a result of this, the weakened Ilyashoja was forced to leave Samarkand and then the entire Movarounnahr.

March to Mongolia. In the meantime, Amir Temur clashed with the governor of Mongolia, Qamariddin, because during this period, his raids on Movarounnahr intensified. In 1370-1371, he invaded Tashkent and Andijan several times, and

the demand returned. In 1376 AD, Qamariddin even conquered a large part of the Ferghana Valley. Amir Temur starts a serious attack on Qamarid to eliminate the constant threat to the northeastern regions of the country. During twenty years (1371-1390), Sahibgiron marched to Mongolia seven times and won victories over the Mongol rulers Angotara and Qamariddin. At the same time, Amir Temur put an end to internal disunity, mutual disputes, as well as pressure from Mongolia in Movarounnahr and Khorzm, and united the peoples and peoples living in this area into a single state. This undoubtedly had a positive effect on the fate of the people of Movarounnahr.

March to Iran and the Caucasus. However, Amir Temur was not satisfied with this. Soon, he marched on the neighboring countries and peoples, and set himself the goal of subduing them and establishing a great centralized kingdom. During this period, the socio-political situation in the Golden Horde, Khorasan and Iran was very favorable for him. Amir Timur started his military campaign from Khurasan. In 1381, he captured Herat. The cities of Sarkhs, Jam, Qawsiya surrendered without a fight. Khurasan, especially its capital Herat, was strategically important and served as a bridge to Iran, Iraq, Syria and other countries. During the years 1381-1384, Amir Temur occupied a large part of Iran. First (1381) Kalot, Turshiz and Sabzavor, then (1383) the fortresses of Zireh, Zova, Farah and Bust of Seistan, and in 1384 the cities of Amul, Sori, Sultaniya and Tabriz of Astrobad region and Azerbaijan were subdued.

Timur's three major wars. Amir Temur invaded Iran, Azerbaijan, Iraq and Sham (Syria) three times. These campaigns are known in history as the "three years", "five years" and "seven years" wars. As a result of the three-year (1386-1388) military campaigns, Jand, Azerbaijan, the northern part of Iraq, Georgia and the lands around Lake Van were occupied.

A three-year march. At the same time, Amir Temur was forced to raise troops three times against Tokhtamish in order to stop the pressure from the north-west, i.e. from the Golden Horde. He was born in 1389 in the Achchik region of Dizaq (Jizzakh), on June 18, 1391 (in the valley of the Kunduzcha (Kondurcha) river, located between the cities of present-day Samara and Chistopol - the city of Kunduzcha), and finally, in 1395 (February 28) in the North In the Caucasus, Tokhtamysh's army was dealt a crushing blow by the Terek River (Battle on the Terek River). He uses a new method of placing the parts of the army on the battlefield and divides them into seven arms. Tokhtamysh Khan divides his army into five hands. The battle takes place in the full advantage of Amir Temur. The remnants of Tokhtamysh's army, which was completely defeated, are pursued to

the Volga. As a result of Amir Temur's military campaigns, cities such as Lower Idil (Volga) region, Saray Berka, Hajitarkhan (Astrakhan) were destroyed. Amir Temur chased Tokhtamish and went to Ryazan region and occupied the city of Yelits. Sh.A. Yazdiy describes Amir Temur's campaign to Moscow as follows: "The host came to Moscow from the cities of Russia. Anda yetkonda Nusratshi'ar party subjugated the province (surroundings of the city) and governors of Andagi. And innumerable goods fell into the hands of Cherik. Azakh (Azov), Kuban and Cherkasy lands also suffered greatly in this war. It is interesting that on the Turotur party of Amir Temur Idil, the son of Urus called Quyrichak oğlan and presented him with the acquired former Khoji ulus.

According to Russian historians B. D. Grekov and A. Yu. Yakubovsky, Amir Temur's victory over Tokhtamysh was of great importance not only for Central Asia, but also for the whole of Eastern Europe, as well as for the unification of scattered Russian principalities. A five-year march. After that, Amir Temur turned all his attention to conquering the lands of Iran, Iraq, Syria, Asia Minor and India. During the five-year (1392-1396) war, he occupied Western Iran, Iraqi Ajam and the Caucasus, as a result of which the rule of the Muzaffarids and Jaloyiris was ended. Amir Temur's campaign against India (May 1398-March 1399) lasted almost eleven months. Amir Temur returned from India with a large booty, including 120 war elephants. Part of the booty was distributed to the army, and the rest was spent on constructions in the cities of Kesh and Samarkand. The Seven Years' War. As a result of Amir Temur's military campaigns in 1399-1404, the major cities of Syria such as Aleppo (Aleppo), Hums, Baalbek (Ba'albek), Dimishq (Damascus) and the Ubilistan region of Iraq (Ancient Cappadocia) and Baghdad, also a large part of Turkey will be conquered. The battle between Amir Temur and Bayazid Yildirim took place on July 25, 1402. According to the sources, the army of the Sultan of Turkey consisted of approximately 160,000 fighters. The Sahibqiran army operates in its traditional battle order. Sahibqiron directly commands the center-arm of Humayun, which is made up of forty troops. Finally, the sultan's troops, unable to withstand the pressure of Amir Temur's units, began to retreat. The fighters under the command of Bayazid will continue to resist until the last breath. In the battle of Ankara, Amir Temur won against one of the great generals of the world, Bayazid Yildirim. The Sultan of Turkey was captured.

The beginning of his march to China. After Amir Temur returned to Samarkand from Asia Minor, on November 27, 1404, he left Samarkand with 200,000 troops for a trip to China. However, the march on China was not possible due to the death of Amir Temur in O'tror (February 18, 1405). Although the news

of Amir Temur's death was kept secret at first, soon this unpleasant news spread throughout the country. Amir Temur's body will be brought to Samarkand and buried.

Conclusion: Amir Temur is a person who rendered incomparable service in the history of our country and the development of Uzbek statehood. Amir Temur is a great figure recognized as a great statesman and famous general in the history of world nations. Unfortunately, the name of Amir Temur was denied during the colonial period and was pushed aside from the generations. However, the time has passed to hide the historical service of Amir Temur, who restored the Uzbek statehood, raised it to a high level of development, spread fame to the world, and kept him in the chain of repression. Thanks to the national independence, we were fortunate to restore the name and the bright image of our grandfather Amir Temur, while objectively covering our mother's history and establishing the historical truth.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати:

1. Boboyev H.B. Amir Temur and the kingdom of the Timurids. - Tashkent: Kamalak, 1996.
2. History of political and legal doctrines / Boboyev H.B., Vohidov H.V., Dadaboyev Y.T., Vohidova D. - Tashkent: 2003.
3. Issues of state and law in Timur's rule: Law. candidate of sciences...dis. autoref. - Tashkent, 2002.
4. Mamatov H.T. Issues of state and law in the rule of Amir Temur. Monograph Y. (co-authored). - Tashkent: New century generation, 2001.

